

Fungicide timing to control rice sheath blight (ShB)

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We tested control of ShB caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* by carbendazim and mancozeb applied at different crop growth and disease development stages during 1987 and 1988 pishanam. Plot size was 5 × 4.5 m, plant spacing 20 × 10 cm, in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fertilizer was applied at 120-162.5-147.5 kg NPK/ha (Ec 0.16, pH 5.8). IR8 was transplanted 30 d after seeding (DAS) on 11 Nov 1987 and 12 Dec 1988.

Fungicides were applied when

Effect of time of application and rate of fungicide for control of rice ShB. Ambasamudram, India, 1987-88.

Fungicide	Time of application	ShB grade	Yield (t/ha)
Mancozeb 1000 g/ha	Disease grade 1	3.6	4.2
Mancozeb 1000 g/ha	Disease grade 3	4.9	4.2
Mancozeb 1000 g/ha	Disease grade 5	5.8	4.1
Carbendazim 250 g/ha	Disease grade 1	3.6	4.2
Carbendazim 250 g/ha	Disease grade 3	5.0	4.2
Carbendazim 250 g/ha	Disease grade 5	5.7	4.1
Carbendazim 250 g/ha	At panicle initiation and heading	2.8	4.3
Mancozeb	At panicle initiation and heading	3.3	4.3
Carbendazim	At heading	3.5	4.2
Mancozeb	At heading	3.4	4.2
No fungicide	—	6.0	4.2
LSD		1.4	ns

disease severity was 1, 3, and 5 and at panicle initiation (PI) (65 DAS) or at heading (80 DAS), or both. Both fungicides sprayed at grade 1 disease stage controlled the disease at grade 3.6 (see table). Spraying at grade 3 or 5 did

not prevent the disease from developing to higher levels. Carbendazim and mancozeb sprayed at PI and 15 d after PI also controlled disease development. Yield differences were not significant. □

Influence of rice plant density and spacing on brown leaf spot incidence

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We studied the influence of seedlings/hill and spacings between hills on brown leaf spot disease Jan-Mar 1989.

Rice cultivar ASD16 was transplanted at one and two seedlings/hill and three spacings in 4- × 5-m plots, in randomized factorial block design with six replications. Normal fertilizer schedule of 100 kg N/ha as urea, 50 kg P/ha as superphosphate, and 50 kg K/ha as potash was applied as basal and topdressing. No fungicide

Influence of plant density (1 or 2 seedlings/hill) and spacing on brown leaf spot incidence in rice. Coimbatore, India, Jan-Mar 1989.

Spacing (cm)	Disease incidence (%)					
	30 d after transplanting			50 d after transplanting		
	1	2	Mean	1	2	Mean
10 × 10	35.56	39.31	37.44	43.19	44.95	44.07
10 × 15	31.61	34.69	33.15	38.57	40.63	39.60
10 × 20	26.17	27.84	27.01	35.20	35.27	35.24
Mean	31.11	33.95	—	38.98	40.29	—
LSD (0.05)						
Seedlings/hill	ns	ns				
Spacing	3.89	4.11				
Interaction	ns	ns				

was applied. Brown leaf spot incidence was assessed at 30 and 50 d after transplanting.

Plots with closer spacing (10 × 10

cm) had significantly higher disease incidence than wider spacing at both density levels and at both observation times (see table). □

Effect of N on false smut (FS) in upland rice

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We studied the effect of N level on FS

caused by *Ustilaginoidea virens* in rainfed rice. The experiment was conducted during 1987 wet season using rice variety Himalaya 741 (CR125-42-5/IR2061-213) at Malan.

Two sources of N, two N levels, and three application schedules were compared with farmer's practice, in randomized block design with three

replications. False-smutted panicles and healthy panicles in 3 random hill samples and false-smutted florets on 30 random panicles were counted in each treatment.

Higher N levels in split applications resulted in higher number of smutted florets/m² (see table). There were no significant differences in

Influence of 2 forms of N fertilizers, N level, and timing of N application on FS severity in rainfed rice.^a Bajaura, India, 1987 wet season.

Treatments			Severity ^b		
N source	Dose (kg/ha)	Time of application	Smutted panicles (%)	Smutted florets (no./m ²)	
Urea	80	100% after germination	2.61 a (8.75)	19.79 ab (198.0)	
Calcium ammonium nitrate	80	100% after germination	2.39 a (6.07)	9.78 ab (141.6)	
Urea	80	50% after germination, 50% 4 wk after	2.68 a (8.68)	8.73 ab (102.3)	
Calcium ammonium nitrate	80	50% after germination, 50% 4 wk after	2.30 a (5.22)	10.06 ab (166.1)	9.73 (144.58)
Urea	80	35% after germination, 65% 4 wk after	2.60 a (7.20)	11.86 b (195.5)	
Calcium ammonium nitrate	80	65% after germination, 65% 4 wk after	1.86 a (3.00)	7.17 ab (70.8)	
Urea	40	100% after germination	1.92 a (4.08)	5.08 a (35.0)	
Calcium ammonium nitrate	40	100% after germination	1.77 a (3.28)	7.40 ab (77.8)	
Urea	40	50% after germination, 50% 4 wk after	2.10 a (4.06)	7.52 ab (69.5)	6.73 (64.6)
Calcium ammonium nitrate	40	50% after germination, 50% 4 wk after	1.81 a (3.62)	6.94 ab (76.1)	
Urea	25	Farmers' practice (4 wk after germination)	1.78 a (2.69)	4.76 a (28.1)	4.26 (28.1)

^aIn a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other by DMRT (P=0.05). ^bSquare root transformed values. Figures in parentheses are original means.

percentage of smutted panicles. Analysis of variance results indicate

that both N source and timing influenced disease severity. □

their location can be determined directly in the field at night.

We released 1,250 marked 1-d-old *N. virescens* adults in late afternoon from a central rice hill to study the effect of host plant resistance on trivial movement of GLH in wetland rice. The fields had been transplanted at 20 × 20 cm with susceptible IR1917 (43 d after transplanting [DT]) and resistant IR29 (31 DT). Although differing by 12 d in age, height and tillering of the two crops were nearly the same.

Sample hills were located in a cruciform design around the source hill, with 2 hills per cardinal direction or 8 hills per distance interval. Marked GLH per hill up to 15 hills from the release center were counted in the evening at 3, 27, 51, and 75 h after release. The number of GLH remaining on the source plant was determined after the last field count.

Leafhopper density in both varieties decreased sharply with increasing distance from the source (see figure). However, the dispersal gradient in resistant IR29 flattened considerably over time compared to that of IR1917.

Dispersal gradients of marked green leafhopper *N. virescens* (Distant) at different times after release in transplanted IR29 and IR1917. IRR, 1982 wet season.

Insect management

Using fluorescent dye to map dispersal pattern of rice green leafhopper (GLH)

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We developed an efficient technique to mark large numbers of GLH for dispersal studies, using a fluorescent dye with excellent adhering properties and low water solubility. One-day-old, greenhouse-reared *Nephotettix virescens* adults were tagged with dry Saturn Yellow[®] (MF-1) fluorescent powder. As the insects were sucked one by one through a plastic tube (1 m long, 1 cm inner diameter) into the collecting vial of an electrical-powered aspirator, they came in contact with the dye which adhered to the ventral side of their

bodies. About 1,000 insects/h could be processed.

The marked insects were placed on a caged rice plant for recovery. Even after grooming, small specks of dye remained on the coxae, femora, abdominal sterna, ovipositor, and in the margin between the wings and pronotum.

In a replicated greenhouse test, the dye (which is insoluble in water) was retained for at least 10 d and did not affect insect survival.

At night, marked insects illuminated with long-wave UV light glow bright yellow. An inexpensive, portable UV lamp can be made from a standard lantern by replacing the original lamp with a G-W long-wave UV unit (GTE Sylvania[®]). GLH is not attracted to the light emitted.

Recapture of fluorescent-dye-marked insects is not necessary to detect their patterns of movement: